

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D4.2

Scientific Aims and Testable
Hypotheses-v1

March 2022

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognized experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalized care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximize project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
EVOLUTION	MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EL
UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AD-GC	Alzheimer's Disease Genetics Consortium
ADNI	Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative
AHI	Apnoea Hypopnea Index
AI	Artificial intelligence
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
APOe	Apolipoprotein E
ASL	Arterial spin labeling
CAI	central apnea index
CBS	Cognitive and Behavioural Symptoms
cCBS	Carer Cognitive and Behavioural Symptoms
CERAD	Consortium to Establish a Registry for Alzheimer's Disease
CFI	Circadian Function Index
CoBraD	Complex Brain Disorders
CPAP	Continuous positive airway pressure
CSA	Central sleep apnea
DWI	Diffusion-Weighted Imaging
EEG	Electroencephalography
ELISA	Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay
ES	Expert System
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FLAIR	Fluid-attenuated inversion recovery
GFAP	Glial fibrillary acidic protein
HC	Healthy Controls
ICD-11	International Classification of Diseases 11th Revision
IEDs	Interictal Epileptiform Discharges
LDA	Linear discriminant analysis
MMSE	Mini-Mental State Examination
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MVR	Mean Variance Regularization
Mx	Month x
ND	Neurodegeneration
NfL	Neurofilament Light Chain
NIV	Non-invasive ventilation
No.	Number
NPS	Neuropsychology
NPT	Neuropsychological Testing
OSA	Obstructive Sleep Apnea
PCA	Principal component analysis
PEA	Proximity Extension Assay

pTAU	phosphorylated-Tau
PSPS	Progressive Supranuclear Palsy Syndrome
PUC	Pilot Use Case
QC	Quality Control
RBD	Rapid eye movement (REM) sleep behavior disorder
ROI	Region of interest
rsfMRI	Resting state functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
RWD	Real World Data
SAMSEG	Sequence Adaptive Multimodal SEGmentation
SDH	Social Determinants of Health
SE	Sleep Efficiency
Simoa	Single-molecule array
SOL	sleep onset latency
SpO2	Saturation of Peripheral Oxygen
SVM	support vector machine
TMT	Trail Making Test
ToC	Table of Contents
UX	User Interface
VLT	Verbal Learning Test
WASO	Wakefulness After Sleep Onset
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 INTRODUCTION

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with CoBraD, as represented in Neurocognitive (e.g., Alzheimer's dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (i.e., Epilepsy) disorders. The principles followed within the MES-CoBraD Project can be generalized for the assessment and management of other Chronic Complex Conditions (CCC) by exploiting advanced analytics modules and RWD acquisition protocols.

Work Package 4 (WP4) defines the methodological process for the analysis of the RWD acquired during pilot data acquisition (WP8) to address the challenges faced in CoBraD and share the results within the Consortium and through scientific publications prior to wider dissemination (WP9). It is one of three WPs (WP4, WP6, WP8) serving scientific objectives whose tasks were distributed for operational efficiency and minimization of errors.

The main objectives of WP4 are:

- › Achieve scientific and social objectives, promote scientific productivity, and solve unforeseen problems
- › Oversee that principles of scientific methods are followed in pursued analyses
- › Perform scientific analyses and disseminate knowledge equitably and according to ethical principles
- › Identify significant results and maximize their impact through multidisciplinary expert contributions
- › Integrate MES-CoBraD Platform Database and Advanced Analytics Modules in maximizing scientific impact

To achieve these goals, eight Work Groups (WG)¹ have been established and organized into three main categories: Complex Brain Disorders, Real World Data and Science of Science work groups. The full list is:

- › Complex Brain Disorders work groups
 - Sleep and Wearables Work Group (WG-SW)
 - Neurodegeneration and Neuropsychological Testing Work Group (WG-ND/NPS)
 - Epilepsy Work Group (WG-Epilepsy)
- › Real World Data work groups
 - Magnetic Resonance Imaging Work Group (WG-MRI)
 - Biofluids Work Group (WG-BF)
- › Science of Science work groups
 - Machine Learning and Expert Systems Work Group (WG-ML)
 - Automatic Quality Control Work Group (WG-autoQC)
 - User Interface Work Group (WG-UX)

¹ Due to the overlap in aims and hypotheses between certain WGs, the Wearables WG was merged with the Sleep WG, and the Neuropsychological Testing WG was merged with the Neurodegeneration WG, explaining the differences in WGs' compared to deliverable D4.1.

Each WG meets at regular intervals to discuss the scientific landscape of their field of expertise and propose research hypotheses and relevant methodologies for their testing, aiming to proceed to its hypothesis testing through a structured collaborative process. Considering the rapid pace of scientific advancement, the relevance, feasibility, and plausibility of hypotheses and their analyses will have to be re-evaluated, modified, updated, or even cancelled, and new ones may need to be considered, depending on current clinical, social, and scientific evidence. The hypotheses throughout the project will have to be re-assessed according to scientific literature, acquired RWD, analysis results and the advancement of technological deliverables.

In this deliverable, we present the initial agreed upon scientific aims and hypotheses to be tested through specific proposed analyses, as suggested during the each WG's activities. Re-evaluation of the suggested hypotheses and methodologies, results, publications, and new hypotheses will be included in future updates of this deliverable (D4.3-D4.5). The final update of the deliverable (D4.6) will present the final outcome of WP4, providing the summary of all scientific publications that resulted in the project, including the final Guidelines for Diagnosis of CoBraD, as well as Guidelines on Safety and Efficacy of Real-World Medical Therapies.

2 WORK GROUPS

2.1 COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS WORK GROUPS

2.1.1 SLEEP AND WEARABLES WORK GROUP (WG- SW)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
Relationship between sleep apnea and cognitive function	Sleep disordered breathing severity will correlate with worse cognition	1. Correlation analysis; sleep apnea variables: AHI, SpO2 min, time below 92% O2; cognitive variables: MMSE, MoCA, bedside NPT, Sleep-mediated Cognitive testing
Relationship between sleep apnea and cognitive function	Self-reported OSA metrics associated with worse cognition	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analyses for cut-off determination. sleep apnea variables: STOP-Bang, PSQI Cognitive variables: MMSE, MoCA, bedside NPT, Sleep-mediated Cognitive testing
Relationship between sleep apnea and neurodegenerative biomarkers	Worse OSA (AHI, SpO2, %time <92%) associated with higher NfL, lower amyloid- β and higher phospho-tau	1. Correlation analysis; 2. Classification analysis (LDA/SVM) based on grouping of OSA severity
Relationship between sleep apnea and neurodegenerative biomarkers	Worse CSA (CAI) associated with higher phospho-tau	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification for cut-off determination
Relationship between sleep apnea and neurodegenerative biomarkers	Worse OSA (AHI, SpO2, %time <92%) associated with more MRI atrophy	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification for cut-off determination
Relationship between circadian rhythm disorders and neurodegenerative biomarkers	More sleep fragmentation (i.e., more arousal events, higher WASO, and lower SE) or fragmented rest-activity rhythm (i.e., higher intra-daily variability, lower inter-daily stability, lower relative amplitude, and lower Circadian Function Index) will be associated with higher neurodegenerative biomarkers levels (phospho-tau, amyloid, NfL)	1. Correlation analysis; 2. Parametric and non-parametric rest-activity rhythm analysis; 3. Classification for cut-off determination
Relationship between sleep apnea and cognitive function	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better cognitive outcomes (executive: trails, digit recall Backwards-Forwards; memory and learning: VLT/CERAD; language: rapid naming)	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification for cut-off determination API for access to PAP device data from the cloud

Relationship between sleep apnea treatment and sleep quality/quantity	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better sleep metrics (TST, SOL, WASO, SE) and actigraphy derived metrics (intra-daily variability and inter-daily stability, relative amplitude, CFI)	1. Correlation analysis; 2. Parametric and non-parametric rest-activity rhythm analysis 3. Classification for cut-off determination
Relationship between sleep apnea and neurodegenerative biomarkers	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better sleep metrics (sleep diary TST, SOL, SE) and neurodegenerative biomarkers levels (phospho-tau, amyloid, NfL)	1. Correlation analysis; Classification for cut-off determination
Relationship between sleep apnea and neurodegenerative biomarkers	Effective treatment with PAP/NIV (AHI, low leak, compliance h/night/month) will be associated with better imaging markers (MRI volumes, ASL, microcortical structure, vascular burden FLAIR)	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification for cut-off determination
Relationship between sleep apnea and neurodegenerative biomarkers	For all cross-sectional hypotheses, baseline status will be predictive of follow up outcomes in respective outcome categories	1. Regression analysis accounting for temporal interval as covariate/cofactor 2. Classification for cut-off determination
Identify prevalence of sleep and circadian rhythm disorders across neurodegenerative and other dementias	Anticipate that each group of dementias will have at least 50-80% chance of having at least one sleep/circadian disorder	1. Frequency analysis of diagnosis/feature x of sleep disorders compared to diagnosis/feature y of neurocognitive disorders
Identify prevalence of sleep and circadian rhythm disorders across neurodegenerative and other dementias	People with a specific neurodegenerative condition will have unique sleep and circadian phenotypes (insomnia in PSPS, RBD in Synucleinopathies)	1. Frequency Analysis. 2. Classification analysis.
Establish normative data for actigraphy	Younger people will not have significantly different intra-daily rhythm variability compared to non-impaired older people who without abnormal neurodegenerative markers	1. Area Under the Curve analysis. 2. Classification analysis
Relationship between dynamic features of cognition and sleep architecture	Sleep mediated cognitive testing will be dependent on specific sleep architecture metrics, and varied by type of cognitive domain (TST for executive and memory; N3 sleep for episodic memory, REM sleep for executive function, cycle integrity with both executive and memory)	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analysis. Sleep mediated tests: Memory (appointment recall), and executive function. Sleep architecture: % of TST as N1, N2, N3, REM; Cycles #, WASO, TST
Relationship between dynamic features of cognition and sleep disordered breathing	Sleep mediated cognitive testing will be dependent on specific sleep disordered breathing metrics, and varied by type of cognitive domain (amount of SpO2 time < 92% but	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analysis. Sleep mediated tests: Memory (appointment recall), and executive function.

not AHI related to executive
function; CSA index related to
executive function more than
memory function)

2.1.2 NEURODEGENERATION AND NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL TESTING WORK GROUP (WG-ND/NPS)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
Use of imaging/genetic/clinical risk scores to predict incidence of late life CoBraD	Multimodal data can help to assess the risk for co-morbid, missed or underdiagnosed CoBraD	Use of external database with healthy subjects (ADNI, AD-GC), to compare to subjects in MES-CoBraD
To develop new tools for quantifying neurodegenerative disease severity	Determinants of dementia/CoBraD severity will differ by subjects' social history	1. Classification analysis (PCA, MVR, clustering k-means)
Replication studies, use our data to replicate previous studies (mostly phenotyping) that had impact but were not replicated	Previous assumptions and single studies will be replicated	Multiple
Prediction of CoBraD co-morbidity (cross sectional data) from single RWD - imaging or questionnaires	The MES-CoBraD protocol will narrow on answers or set of questions that identify CoBraD comorbidity	Multiple
Prediction of CoBraD incidence (longitudinal)	There will be predictors of incidence over time based on RWD and MES-CoBraD protocol	Cox, fine-grey, other hazard models
Assessing the utility of self-administered symptoms checklist for CoBraD diagnosis	Self-administered symptoms checklist will be useful in diagnosing CoBraD in timely manner	Compare findings on neuropsychology, physical examination and establish consensus to self-reported forms
To assess the impact of SDH on ND severity and RWD variability	We hypothesize that lower SDH will be associated with worse ND severity	Cluster analysis of SDH, PCA, logistic regression, L2-regularized algorithms
To create SDH signatures and test it across samples	The use of multimodal data will allow the creation of a SDH signature	Neurophysiology data based logistic regression
Assess dynamic features of cognition in early diagnosis and prognosis of neurocognitive disorders	Sleep mediated cognitive testing will be more sensitive than routine cognitive tests in identifying neurocognitive disorders early in the disease course as represented through history and expert assessments subjective	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analysis. Sleep mediated tests: Memory (appointment recall), and executive function Routine tests: Bedside NPT Expert assessment: ICD-11 diagnosis by physician; History: Subjective complaint questionnaires

Assess dynamic features of cognition in early diagnosis and prognosis of neurocognitive disorders	Sleep mediated cognitive testing will be more sensitive than routine cognitive tests in identifying neurocognitive disorders early in the disease course as represented in neurodegenerative biomarkers	1. Correlation analysis 2. Classification analysis. Sleep mediated tests: Memory (appointment recall), and executive function Routine tests: Bedside NPT Biomarkers: MRI volume, cortical diffusivity, NfL, phospho-tau, β -amyloid
Assess history questionnaires in phenotyping neurocognitive disorders	CBS, cCBS, and Daily Ability questionnaires will allow classifying neurocognitive disorders in major diagnostic domains with high accuracy	1. Classification analysis. Diagnostic gold standard: ICD11 code by expert assessment
Assess history questionnaires in phenotyping neurocognitive disorders	CBS, cCBS, and Daily Ability questionnaires will reduce time of visit significantly (criterion: >15 min clinical significance)	1. ANOVA between use and non-use of questionnaires in assessing neurocognitive disorders
Assess history questionnaires in phenotyping neurocognitive disorders	CBS, cCBS, and Daily Ability questionnaires will minimize chance of unnecessary testing	1. Non-parametric frequency testing. Unnecessary testing measured as # of tests that did not change diagnosis or management

2.1.3 EPILEPSY WORK GROUP (WG-EPILEPSY)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
Explore EEG background activities in relation to the results of Neuropsychology assessment	EEG background slowing will correlate to worse Neuropsychological testing scores	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG analysis
Explore EEG background activities in relation to brain MRI	EEG slowing will correlate with more brain atrophy	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG to confirm level of slowing. Asymmetry in slow EEG activity and relation with MRI findings
Explore EEG epileptiform activities in relation to Neuropsychology scores and domains	Higher amount of (by definition) IEDs will be related to worse Neuropsychology scores	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for IEDs detection. Number of IEDs related to Neuropsychology test results
Explore EEG epileptiform activities in relation to Neuropsychology and cognition	Topography of IEDs (by definition IEDs) will be related to specific types of cognitive decline	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for IEDs detection. Localization of IEDs related to Neuropsychology test results

Explore relation of EEG background activity with risk for seizures	Quantitative EEG analysis will help identify number/type of recorded seizures	Quantitative analysis tools such as FFT; Correlation analysis; Regression analysis
Explore EEG ictal or epileptiform activities in relation to medication	Quantitative and visual EEG analysis (IEDs or ictal changes) will correlate with drug administration time, type, and dose	Visual and Quantitative EEG analysis tools such as FFT; Correlation analysis; Regression analysis
Explore relation of stress, EEG and seizures	EEG will relate to stress measurement (hair cortisol) and stress assessment scales (Perceived stress scale, Life adverse events). The correlation might apply to EEG background frequencies or the number of epileptiform discharges. Hair cortisol will correlate to frequency of clinical or electrographic seizures.	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for IEDs and EEG seizures detection; Correlation analysis; Regression analysis
Explore relation of stress with Complex Brain Disorders	Hair cortisol levels will be different in the CoBraD (Epilepsy, sleep disorders and neurocognitive disorders)	Cortisol levels compared with different types/subtypes of disorders; Correlation analysis; Regression analysis
Explore possible relation of EEG background with current medication	EEG background frequencies correlates with type/doses of antiepileptic drugs	Quantitative analysis tools such as FFT; Correlation analysis; Regression analysis
Explore EEG runs of epileptiform activity (or subclinical seizures) with biomarkers of Complex Brain Disorders and Neuropsychology testing scores	Biomarkers' levels and neuropsychology scores for dementia patients will be different for patients with subclinical IEDs runs or subclinical seizure EEG activity	Visual analysis or/and quantitative EEG for runs of IEDs detection or subclinical electrographic seizures. Localization/number tested against Neuropsychology scores and biomarkers levels
Explore actigraphy data to EEG and clinical onset of seizures	Actigraphy changes might be stereotyped before onset of seizures	Actigraphy data analyzed in conjunction with EEG ictal data and time of clinical seizure onset; Regression analysis

2.2 REAL WORLD DATA WORK GROUPS

2.2.1 MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING WORK GROUP (WG-MRI)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
Quantify (and correct) T1w acquisition difference over Region of Interest (ROI) volume in CoBraD	We will find site differences. Such differences can be corrected with harmonization methods (e.g Combat)	Compute ROI volumes from FLAIR scans (obtained with SAMSEG). Evaluate harmonization methods by group-wise comparisons
Test between defacing algorithms	Newer versions will overcome hacking-strategies of re-identifying participants	Multiple
Automatic Quality Control (QC) of MRI	QC measures will help to separate useless MRI from informative ones.	MRI QC
Individual reports based on normalized data (w-score / z-score)	We will be able to generate normative data from age-sex match healthy groups across sites.	Compute z-score for individual participants compared to same CoBraD group and versus Healthy controls
Support Vector Machine learning (SVM) (or other machine learning) to predict (clinical/NPS/biomarkers) missing information	SVM models trained with MRI-driven RWD, will allow to predict specific missing data, especially, those markers related to neurodegeneration and cognitive decline	Define training and test samples. Hyperparameter fitting with backprop. Check accuracy (i.e similarity)
Prediction of future outcomes in epilepsy/stroke patients (based on rsfMRI or DWI connectome)	The combination of (1) identification of hot-spots and (2) using spreading models based on connectomics will improve the prediction of clinical evolution/recovery of the participants with epilepsy or stroke	Prepare a connectome-matrix with ROI-ROI connections. Implement a diffusion propagation algorithm. Implement prediction scores
CoBraD differences in brain structure alterations	We will identify a structural pattern that allows to differentiate between the different CoBraD, accounting by co-occurrence of disease. We will also identify a set of cortical regions that are common between CoBraDs	Group comparison of the different CoBraD versus healthy controls. Compute map-extend similarity
Structural patterns differences between socio-economical groups within CoBraDs	Several CoBraD structural pattern differences, compared to healthy controls, will differ accounting by socio-economical group differences	Voxel/vertex-wise Group comparison within each CoBraD, between different socio-economic groups

2.2.2 BIOFLUIDS WORK GROUP (WG-BF)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
To investigate the relationship between Alzheimer or Parkinson symptoms (motor and cognitive) and central or peripheral insulin levels.	Alzheimer or Parkinson Disease progression is negatively correlated with insulin level/function.	Correlation analysis (symptoms vs insulin levels) or predictive models (Insulin levels predicting PD or AD stages, controlled by the presence of risk genes [e.g. APOe3])
CoBraD share pathological mechanisms and therefore biomarkers. We aim to reliably identify these diseases by screening for several biomarkers.	Differences and similarities in neurological biomarkers among CoBraD will be found	Analysis of several biomarkers (e.g. neurofilaments, amyloid protein (Ab40 & 42), Tau, pTau231, GFAP, insulin, cortisol, and others ²) via SIMOA, PEA and ELISA techniques.

2.3 SCIENCE OF SCIENCE WORK GROUPS

2.3.1 MACHINE LEARNING AND EXPERT SYSTEMS WORK GROUP (WG-ML)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
Assess ES's usefulness for Diagnosis of CoBraD	The ES will optimize the diagnostic process with regard to time, cost, and outcomes	We will use a variety of models (e.g., PUC4's model and the gold standards) to implement them in ES. We will use these models to test the ES's hypotheses. The ES will provide metrics to check the significance and the specificity of the Diagnosis and the Treatment.
	The diagnosis for a given patient will affect their unique case outcomes	
	The use of the ES will improve cost-effective diagnosis.	
Assess ES's usefulness for Treatment of CoBraD	The ES will provide more accurate and comprehensive diagnosis	The knowledge base that will be implemented will be updated with the gold standards and our hypotheses outcome and will assist the ES in making decisions.
	The ES will allow for more cost-effective treatment decisions	
	The ES will increase the chance of implementing evidence-based treatment options	
	The ES will increase the chance of better outcomes	

² A full description of the proteomic variables that can be measured from MES-CoBraD participants' biological samples is annexed (i.e., ANNEX VI) to deliverable D3.1 – Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation.

2.3.2 AUTOMATIC QUALITY CONTROL WORK GROUP (WG-AUTOQC)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
Understand how to properly anonymize the input data	The input data contains personal information, then they will need to be de-personalized before being ingested into the MES-CoBraD cloud platform	Anonymization and/or pseudo-anonymization through a tool deployed directly within the Local Area Network of the clinics
Define a common internal data model for the MES-CoBraD components	The input data are very heterogenous in terms of data structure and models. In order to be comfortably analyzed within the platform they will be "harmonized" in a common data-model shared among the MES-CoBraD components.	Each of the possible data-sources are analyzed and a common data model (possibly standard and well known to the scientific community) will be used.
Improve the AI models accuracy	The data cleaning and harmonization will allow to train more accurate AI models.	Train models both on raw and clean data and compare the resulting model accuracy.

2.3.3 USER INTERFACE WORK GROUP (WG-UX)

Aim	Hypothesis	Methods
To assess the impact of user experience variables on users' intentions of future use of the MES-CoBraD System	Based on UX, Usability and Technology Acceptance/Adoption literature we will identify some most likely variables determinants of user's intentions of future use of the system.	Statistical methods to be employed are Regression Analysis, Path Analysis or Structural Equation Modeling.
To find out the determinants of main user experience variables	Based on a literature review of UX, Usability and Technology Acceptance/Adoption we will identify most likely determinants of UX variables.	Statistical methods to be employed are Regression Analysis, Path Analysis or Structural Equation Modeling.

